

MICROCELLULAR GRAPHITIC FOAM PROCESSING

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SUMMARY: This paper reviews the experimental work to develop processing conditions for pitch foams. The foams are produced by dissolving a gas into the pitch under pressure. After the appropriate amount of time has lapsed the pressure is released, the gas nucleates bubbles, and these bubbles grow, forming the pitch into the foam structure. The resultant foamed pitch is then stabilized in an oxygen environment. At this point a rigid structure exists with some mechanical integrity. The foam is then carbonized to 800°C followed by a graphitization to 2500°C. The shear action of the bubbles growing aligns the graphitic planes along the foam struts to provide the ideal structure for good mechanical properties. Variations of the blowing temperature, blowing pressure and saturation time results in foams of various open pore sizes. This study showed the final temperature and the duration of the hold time most effected the foam structure. A lower final temperature and a longer hold time produced a foam with a uniform porosity foam with a very small bubble size.

KEYWORDS: structural foams, graphitic foams, open-cell foams, processing

INTRODUCTION

Structural composites are based on disconnected carbon fibers integrated in some type of matrix. The strength and stiffness of commercial carbon fibers are due to the graphitic morphology that originates from the melt spinning of the precursor pitch. If an interconnected network of struts could be produced which possessed a similar morphology to the carbon fiber, a new generation of composite reinforcement could emerge. Foams are an example of such materials with an open cell structure being the desired architecture. Microcellular, open cell foams can be produced from anisotropic pitch with graphitic planes aligned along the struts. The process sequence includes blowing, stabilizing, carbonizing, then graphitizing the foam, similar to the process for manufacturing pitch-based carbon fibers. A foam could be blown into a mold for net-shape composites or co-processed with fibers for anisotropic reinforcements. Model graphitic foams were predicted [1] to have a compression modulus of approximately 2 GPa with a density of about 0.1 gm/cm³. Not many other foams or core materials have a density and compression modulus near these values.

The original process for fabricating microcellular foams was developed by Suh *et al.* [2-3] They demonstrated microcellular foams could be produced from amorphous polymers by saturating the polymer with a gas then heating above the glass transition temperature. The sudden release of pressure resulted in a foam of uniformly distributed pores. Dutta, *et al.* [4] modified this process by saturating with nitrogen under pressure to get better solubility of nitrogen into pitch. In this process, the solubility of nitrogen into the pitch is critical to foam

fabrication. Therefore, they first melted the pitch in a steady flow of nitrogen. The pitch was then saturated with nitrogen gas and held for 10 minutes before dropping the pressure and temperature suddenly.

The current method of fabricating microcellular foams is a variation of both the Suh and Dutta work. It includes a slight initial pressurization before the pitch is heated. Thus, the pitch is under a slight pressure during heating and is further pressurized at the final temperature. For this process pressure, temperature and time are the controllable parameters and can be varied to produce foams with various magnitudes and types (closed or open) of porosity. Therefore, this study was done to determine the effect of these parameters on the final foam structure.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Foams were processed from AR pitch manufactured by Mitsubishi Gas Chemical Co. The pitch is produced by the catalytic polymerization of naphthalene and supplied in a pellet form. Manufacturing data claims the softening temperature is 239°C and the material is 100 percent anisotropic. The glass transition temperature occurs over a temperature range of 230 to 260°C.

Processing

The pitch pellet was jet-milled into particles of an average size of 1-3 microns. Approximately 10 grams of jet-milled pitch was pressed into a 5.7 cm diameter puck. The pitch puck was then placed in a Parr pressure reactor and heated (under a slight nitrogen pressure) at 3°C/min to the desired final temperature. When the puck reached the final temperature additional nitrogen was added to obtain the final desired pressure and the entire system was held at these conditions for a determined amount of time. The pressure was abruptly vented to the atmosphere. Figure 1 shows a process cycle, with a sample rate of one data point per 5 seconds. This processing created the foam structure to be further analyzed. Further processing was required to transform it from a pitch to a carbonaceous foam. After blowing, the foam was quickly removed from the reactor and placed in a 150 to 175°C oven. The foam was then cooled to room temperature and weight and dimensional measurements were taken. The foams were then oxygen stabilized in a forced air oven at 220°C until a weight gain of approximately 7 percent had been reached. Samples were then carbonized with a 60°C/hour heating rate to 850°C in a nitrogen environment.

Figure 1: Foam Blowing Process Cycle

Characterization

Physical evaluations included weights and dimensional measurements. These measurements were taken after puck fabrication, after foaming, and after carbonization to give a non-destructive indication of any differences produced by the various processing conditions. The completely processed foams were examined under both optical and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and measurements of the pore size, pore shape, and amount of open porosity were made. The relative pore size was measured using the SEM images. All samples were examined at the same magnification and pore sizes measured using arbitrary rulers in the imaging software program. Averages were calculated using 101 randomly chosen pores. The standard deviation of the pore size was also calculated and assumed to be a measure of the uniformity of the foam porosity.

Finally, compression tests were performed on samples from the experimental conditions that produced testable materials. The test configuration basically followed ASTM D695, however sample sizes were dictated by the size of the fabricated foam. From the tests both compression strength and modulus were calculated.

Design of Experiment

A 2⁴ half factorial design of experiment was performed to look at the effect of four process parameters; the initial pressure, final temperature, final pressure, and the length of the hold time at the final conditions. Table 1 provides the experimental values for each parameter and Table 2 the conditions of each experimental run.

Table 1: Experimental Values

Initial Pressure (P _i):	1380 kPa (-)	3450 kPa (+)
Final Temperature(T _f):	250°C (-)	270°C (+)
Final Pressure (P _f):	6900 kPa (-)	10,350 kPa (+)
Hold Duration (t):	15 minute (-)	30 minute (+)

Table 2: Experimental Run Conditions

Sample #	P _i	T _f	P _f	t
1	+	+	+	+
2	-	+	+	-
3	+	-	+	-
4	-	-	+	+
5	+	+	-	-
6	-	+	-	+
7	+	-	-	+
8	-	-	-	-

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For all experiments, foams were created with varying microstructures and compression properties. Figure 2 shows SEM images of the extreme microstructures produced by varying the process parameters. The foam in Figure 2a was processed with higher initial pressure, the lower final temperature and final pressure, and the longer hold time. Figure 2b was processed with higher initial pressure and higher final temperature, lower final pressure, and the shorter hold time. The sample represented in Figure 2a had much more uniform porosity with a smaller bubble size than the non-uniform, large sized pores shown in Figure 2b. Figure 2a represented the more desired foam structure.

Figure 2: SEM Images of foam samples,
(a) small, uniform porosity, (b) large, non-uniform pores.

The volumetric change due to foaming was measured by comparing the pre-foamed puck volume to the foam volume before stabilization. Each process parameter was plotted versus the volumetric change to determine which had the most influence, Figure 3. As can be seen the only parameter that had any effect is the hold duration at the final temperature after the final pressure has been added. A shorter hold time resulted in a larger expansion in the foamed pitch. The longer time at the final conditions allowed the system to equilibrate and more nitrogen was able to diffuse into and uniformly disperse throughout the pitch. When the pressure was released the nitrogen nucleated and grew bubbles and quickly produced an open-cell structure. As the open cell structure formed, the nitrogen was able to diffuse out of the foam and bubble growth was terminated.

The final temperature had a minor secondary effect on the volumetric change. The foams produced with a lower final temperature did not expand as much as the ones made at the

higher temperature. At the lower temperature, the pitch had a higher viscosity and could keep more nitrogen trapped. When the pressure was released the nitrogen expanded and quickly created an open cell structure. The open cells allowed the nitrogen to vent to the atmosphere and minimized volume expansion. At the higher temperature, less nitrogen was available for bubble growth and an open structure was not produced until much later in the foaming process. Therefore, a larger expansion in volume occurred at the higher final temperature.

Figure 3: Volumetric Increase from puck to foam as a function of (a) initial pressure, (b) final temperature, (c) final pressure, and (d) hold duration.

The average pore size was plotted against each of the process parameters, Figure 4, to determine what were the effects of each parameter on the pore size. The results showed the final temperature had the largest influence on pore size. The higher final temperature produced foams with larger size pores than the lower final temperature. At the lower temperature the pitch has a much higher viscosity and thus a much greater ability to keep the nitrogen trapped. The greater amount of nitrogen trapped inside the pitch the more bubbles that could nucleate and/or the more nitrogen there is available to grow the bubbles. The viscosity of the pitch was high enough to restrict the bubble growth to keep the pores small.

When the results from the volume increase were compared to the relative pore size it was determined the smaller pore size also had the lower volume increase. Apparently the nitrogen nucleated bubbles and as they grew they formed an open-cell foam structure that allowed the

nitrogen to diffuse out before the bubbles grew to a larger size or coalesced to form larger pores. This would allow for a high density of very small bubbles.

Figure 4: Average pore size as a function of (a) initial pressure, (b) final temperature, (c) final pressure, and (d) hold duration.

Compression tests were only done on material from experiments 3,4,5,7 in Table 1. These were the only experiments that produced samples large enough to make compression samples. The compression strength was plotted versus process parameters and shown in Figure 5. The higher final temperature produced lower strength foams than the lower final temperature. This trend could be correlated with the relative pore size. The larger pore size produced a foam with lower compression strength. This was due to the smaller strut size in the larger pore foam. As the bubble grows the strut becomes more elongated and thinner than the struts of the smaller pore foam. The pore size can be explained by the difference in the viscosity of the pitch at 250°C and 270°C. At 270°C the pitch molecules were more mobile and the nitrogen did not saturate the pitch as much as it did at 250°C.

Figure 5: Compression strength as a function of (a) initial pressure, final temperature, (c) final pressure, and (d) hold duration.

CONCLUSIONS

From the experiments the amount of pressure does not significantly contribute to the final foam structure. Foams processed at the high and low levels had the same structure. Therefore, the pressures that were studied were sufficient to diffuse nitrogen into the puck. Further studies need to be conducted to determine the lower limit on the amount of pressure required to produce a foam structure.

The final temperature did produce some variation in the foam materials. At the lower temperature the pitch is within the glass transition temperature range. In this range the material had more integrity and was able to restrict gas flow and bubble growth. When the foam was at 250°C and the pressure was released the pitch was viscous enough to restrict bubble growth and produce a small pore size foam. At 270°C the pitch viscosity was low enough so the nitrogen was able to diffuse in and out easily. When the pressure was released the nitrogen nucleated bubbles and the bubbles grew rapidly leaving a large cell foam behind.

The hold time produced variations in the different foam samples. A more uniform pore distribution was produced with the longer hold time. This could be attributed to the system have more time to reach an equilibrium at the final processing conditions. After the final

temperature is reached and the final pressure is applied, the 30 minute hold time allowed the pitch system to equilibrate and the nitrogen to further diffuse into the pitch. The more nitrogen in the pitch the more gas available to nucleate and grow bubbles. Experiments with additional hold times need to be conducted to determine the effect longer and shorter hold times have on the foam structure.

The most desirable foam structure was produced with a final temperature of 250°C and these conditions were maintained for 30 minutes before the 10350 kPa of pressure was suddenly released. These parameters allowed nitrogen to diffuse into the pitch, yet did not weaken the pitch's ability to restrict bubble growth to produce the small pores. This foam structure had the desired uniform, small pore size. The compression strength of this structure was the highest value achieved for all of the foam experiments.

REFERENCES

1. Hall, R.B. and Hager, J.W., "Graphitic Foams as Potential Structural Materials", *21st Biennial Conference on Carbon Extended Abstracts*, 1993, pp. 100-101.
2. Colton, J.S. and Suh, N.P., "The Nucleation of Microcellular Thermoplastic Foam with Additives: Part I: Theoretical Consideration", *Polymer Engineering and Science*, Vol.27, No.7, 1987, pp.485-499.
3. Colton, J.S. and Suh, N.P., "Nucleation of Microcellular Foam: Theory and Practice", *Polymer Engineering and Science*, Vol.27, No.7, 1987, pp.500-503.
4. Dutta, D., Hill, C.S., and Anderson, D.P., "Processing, Structure, and Morphology of Graphitic Carbon Foams Produced from Anisotropic Pitch", *Novel Forms of Carbon II, MRS Symposium Proceedings*, Vol. 349, pp. 61-66.
5. Hager, J.W., Anderson, D.P., and Roy A.K., "Structure and Properties of Carbon Foams from Pitch and Phenolic Precursors", *22nd Biennial Conference on Carbon Extended Abstracts*, 1995, pp.106-107.
6. Hager, J.W., Anderson, D.P., and Roy, A.K., "Progress in Open-Celled Carbon Foams", *Proceedings of 40th International SAMPE Symposium (Closed Sessions)*, 1995, pg. 42-48.
7. Hager, J.W., and Anderson, D.P., "Idealized Ligament Formation and Geometry in Open-Celled Foams", *21st Biennial Conference on Carbon Extended Abstracts*, 1993, pp. 102-103.
8. Anderson, D.P., Gunnison, K.E., and Hager, J.W., "Ligament Structure of Open-Cell Carbon Foams and the Construction of Models Based on that Structure". *Novel Forms of Carbon, MRS Symposium Proceedings*, Vol. 270, 1992, pp.47-52.